

**MAPPING GLOBAL SOUTH IN THE SECURITY AGENDA: AN
INVESTIGATION OF INDIA'S CONTRIBUTION TO PEACE-
BUILDING ASSISTANCE IN POST-CONFLICT STATES**

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Abstract

The early 1990s witnessed peaceful settlements of civil wars through international settlements and mediation, which led to the concept of peace-making. However, such approaches were limited due to their failures in negotiating settlements. Therefore, in response, the idea was shifted to peace-building implementation. Within the United Nations, the officials and the West primarily focussed on the West coalitions and direct administration over the governing gaps, civil affairs, electoral and policing tasks, disarmament and humanitarian assistance to the post-conflict states. Nevertheless, these approaches were restricted in terms of their motivation and guiding principles in the global south. As a recipient as well as a provider of peace-building and development assistance itself, India did not follow the conventional idea of peace-building. Therefore, India becomes an imperative case as a norm entrepreneur who is shaping and evolving norms around the idea of peace and peace-building.

It marked a significant change as India developed its own understanding of peace-building assistance separate from the West. Its historical and lived experiences and socio-economic condition as a developing state provided India with a prime location, driving its motive through the emotional and ideational consideration to express solidarity with other developing states. In the changed geo-political contexts, India brought an alternative perspective of peace-building as developmental assistance, focussing largely on capacity gaps instead of governing gaps. As one of the major drivers in the global south, the study attempts to focus on why India's approach to development and peace-building assistance captured the attention in the twenty-first

century and how it differs from Western assistance. It emphasises the benefits of diverse methods instead of an attempt for uniformity and singularity in peace-building assistance. Lastly, it will discuss its challenges during peacekeeping and building missions in post-conflict states.

Keywords: eacebuilding, norms, India, capacity building, women, peace and security.

Introduction

During the nineteenth and twentieth century, a period where the first steps towards a collective effort to maintain peace and security were gradually formalised and institutionalised, the great powers exercised a prominent role (Bellamy and Williams, 2011). During the Concert of Europe and the League of Nations, the concept of 'peacekeeping' was a crucial part of the duties assigned to Western European states. These assignments established a clear hierarchy in the international community. In both periods, peace-building attempts were closely tied to the strategic interests of the European great powers. This included deploying humanitarian operations to protect key geopolitical areas, authorising international forces to maintain colonial positions, and other military activities aimed at suppressing any attempt to question their domestic and international status quo. These actions were taken to protect their strategic interests and maintain their superiority in the international community (Macqueen, 2006). However, the idea started witnessing limitations and failures in negotiated settlements in Rwanda and former Yugoslavia with the return of violence. Therefore, the international community began to look for 'peace implementation' (Call, 2015) with a prime focus on enhancing the international political will, capacities and knowledge for better implementation. The 1990s witnessed a rise in models of peace-making with prominence in peaceful settlements through international negotiations and mediation, including Namibia, Cambodia and Guatemala (UN Peacekeeping).

The idea of 'multi-dimensional peacekeeping' rose from the UN Secretariat as an idea for peace implementation, focusing on civil requirements, monitoring civil, political, electoral and human rights and humanitarian affairs and policing tasks. Within the UN agencies, peace-building was the term used for policy and project documents for developmental work in fragile post-conflict states. The theory and

practice of peace-building are mainly derived from two major UN operations in Kosovo and East Timor (Hearn, Bujones and Kugel, 2014). Although the term emerged in the late 1990s and early twenty-first century, its conceptualisation and the term itself first emerged decades ago through the work of Johan Galtung, who called for the creation of peace-building structures to promote sustainable peace by addressing the "root causes" of violent conflict and supporting indigenous capacities for peace management and conflict resolution (Galtung, 1976).

Peace-building became a familiar concept within the UN following Boutros Boutros-Ghali's 1992 report (UN et al. Office, 2010), *An Agenda for Peace*, which defined peace-building as action to solidify peace and avoid relapse into conflict. In 2000, the Brahimi Report defined it as "activities undertaken on the far side of the conflict to reassemble the foundations of peace and provide the tools for building on those foundations, something that is more than just the absence of war" (UN Peace-building support, 2010). The Secretary-General's Policy Committee has described peace-building thus: "Peace-building involves a range of measures targeted to reduce the risk of lapsing or relapsing into conflict by strengthening national capacities at all levels for conflict management and to lay the foundations for sustainable peace and development". These developments within international institutions assume that they build 'peace' (Chandler, 2012) by applying similar liberal states' frameworks and practices of democratic politics and free market policies (Conning and Call, 2017). However, the recurring violent conflicts provided the picture otherwise in the wake of the poor record of the peace-building model in countries like Afghanistan, Bosnia-Herzegovina, the Democratic Republic of the Congo, Iraq, and Sierra Leone, which provided a space for global south states such as India as key players to (re)shape the idea of peace-building itself.

Therefore, this paper seeks to answer certain prime questions, focusing on the new approaches to peace-building from the global south. What makes the case of India imperative to understand the peace-building discourse? What are the implications of these approaches on the traditional understanding of peace-building? How are these new approaches influencing the way the United Nations has understood the idea of peace-building? What innovations, lessons, best practices, and challenges have emerged with the rise of new actors and approaches in the field of peace-building?

(Re)shaping Peace-building: Changing Norms and Players

Due to the failure of peace-building to deliver sustained peace, a push from post-colonial states against Western ideological construct or dominance emerged to turn to the Global South as a source for more legitimate and effective responses. Hence, debates over institutions associated with peace-building have become a central focus of post-conflict contestation. Nevertheless, to combat peace-building failures, the United Nations (UN) Peace-building Commission was created in 2005 as the sole UN organ where UN member states come together to discuss peace and security issues outside of the General Assembly (Jenkins, 2013). While parts of the UN's peace-building architecture, such as the UN Peace-building Fund, proved innovative and effective, the performance overall of the UN's peace-building architecture has not met expectations (De Coning & Stamnes, 2016). Two major UN reviews were undertaken in 2015, one taking stock of peace operations and the other assessing the peace-building architecture.

With new actors playing a key role in (re)shaping peace-building norms, new dimensions also emerged in understanding the idea of peace along with negotiations post-2015 development agenda (Richmond & Tellidis, 2013). The Sustainable Development Goal of Agenda 2030, especially in Goal 16, aims to promote peaceful and inclusive societies for sustainable development, to provide access to justice for all, and to build effective, accountable, and inclusive institutions at all levels. lastly, how the idea and framework of peace-building is towards sustainable peace (SDG 16). In another development, a group of 19 self-identified fragile states like East Timor and Liberia have been at the forefront of the New Deal (International Dialogue on Peace-building and State Building 2017; Wyeth 201). By transforming it into context-specific, it seeks to change the way international assistance by placing themselves in the driver's seat to determine the cause of fragility and to plan its own path to resilience. The approach of the UN Secretariat and of European institutions, on the one hand, has been largely top-down, institution-focused (instead of process-focused), state-centric and short-term (Call & Collin, 2015; Stamnes, 2016).

With new actors like the BRICS (Brazil, Russia, India, China, and South Africa) (de Coning et al. 2014) along with various regional powers like Turkey and Indonesia, there has been a rise in their own political as well

as technical approaches to peace-building by being "donors" (de Carvalho & de Coning, 2013) They are also seen as an alternative or antidote to dominant liberal approaches (Campbell et al., 2011). These antidotes mark these countries being the norm entrepreneurs. Barnett and Finnemore take the idea of norms further to study the processes of how a norm emerges, cascades and internalises in any international organisation (Barnett & Finnemore, 1960). One such norm entrepreneur is India. India has its historical and post-colonial experiences and socioeconomic conditions as a developing state. It has provided India with a prime location, driving its motive through the emotional and ideational significance of expressing solidarity with other developing states in conflict situations.

Understanding India's approach to Peace-building

What makes India distinctive and interesting to study is its different historical experiences, socio-economic conditions, and lived experiences (Choeden, 2023). By sharing the benefits of its own lived experiences and its historical struggle and assistance, India has contributed to building strong and peaceful countries and regions across the globe (Singh, 2017).

The conflict-affected states have been a recipient of India's assistance with technical, training, and educational programs within their given socio-economic context. Being one of the major recipients of development aid, till 2004, India has provided development assistance to many post-colonial states in their state-building efforts since 1947 (Conning and Call, 2017). During the Cold War era, Despite being confronted with major security challenges, India also made a major contribution to UN peacekeeping operations to assist developing countries in managing conflicts (Conning et al, 2017). This has been done to express solidarity with other developing countries during the NAM movement. When internal conflicts became a major phenomenon in the post-Cold War era, Western countries developed a practice of labelling conflict-affected states as 'fragile states' (Chodon, 2023). They developed different policies and funding instruments for such countries under the rubric of peace-building. Against this politics of labelling, India did not adopt a similar differential treatment of the countries affected by conflict, nor did it adopt a separate peace-building policy. It continued to provide development assistance for the reconstruction of

the conflict-affected states. This assistance is similar to peace-building assistance provided by developed countries.

Therefore, India does not distinguish between developmental assistance and peace-building (Choedon, 2021). The Indian peacekeepers in the UN operations are engaged in stabilising the conflict-affected states and providing basic services to the conflict-affected people. The Indian peacekeepers are regarded as early peacebuilders (Choedon, Singh and Conning) as they carry out various social and development activities in their deployment areas. As of Nov. 2023, India has provided 90,348.89 Crore as a grant and loan within its developmental partnership, with an increase of 28.3% from previous years to neighbouring countries (MEA, LOC 2023).

Peace-building as Developmental Assistance: Creating Norms

The lived experiences as a developing state, carrying a colonial history, the similar experiences of the global south due to colonialism, fragility, conflicts, poverty and lack of infrastructure provided India a central location to reshape the norms around peace-building as developmental assistance. The idea of "south-south cooperation" thus, can be argued to begin with mutual understanding, historical legacies, lived experiences and development aid and partnership -(Singh, 2017). Till 2023, India has provided peace-building assistance as development aid in various countries, from Cuba and Ghana to Fiji.

Fig.1 Source: MEA India: https://www.mea.gov.in/Images/amb1/lu3714_aane1.pdf

With programs spanning all continents, India has provided development aid on a worldwide scale. India has demonstrated its broad range of actions in development assistance and its long-term perspective by helping in Africa and Afghanistan, among other places (Singh, 2017). India does not differentiate peace-building assistance from development assistance. Instead, India focuses on addressing capacity gaps in conflict-affected states, while DAC countries prioritise addressing the governance gap (Arora, 2017, p. 243; Sharan et al., 2013). Along similar lines, it has also launched the 'India Development Initiative' to assist other developing countries. Following this, the allocation of development assistance was increased, and a new mechanism called the lines of credits (LOCs) system was introduced, causing India to be a major provider of development and peace-building aid on a global scale. These developments changed India from an aid receiver to an aid donor (Choedon, 2023). India's development and peace-building assistance in 2000 was less than US\$500 million and reached a high of US\$1.32 billion in 2019–2020 (Mullen, 2019).

India's developmental assistance has been mainly in three ways: Grants and loans, lines of credit (concessional loans) and capacity building (MEA India). These three areas encompass a wide variety of aid as peace-building. It includes not just the construction of major buildings or focussing on governing gaps in post-conflict states, but rather the capacity gaps by assisting in health and sanitation, food, education (scholarships and study tours), political and economic cooperation, etc.

Fig. 2 Country-wise fund disbursed: ₹1,219.7cr (2023-24).

Source: <https://meadashboard.gov.in/indicators/92>

These lines of credit provide various projects to sustain peace. For instance, Low-cost housing and economic building projects in Burkina Faso, two hydro-electric projects in the Central African Republic, a Sugarcane development and irrigation project in Ghana, Post Earthquake rehabilitation projects in Nepal and the Rehabilitation of Kankesanthurai Harbour in Sri Lanka, etc. Beyond this, India has also a capacity-building program (GOI, LOC, 2019). These capacity-building programs are associated with the development of human resources in which the capabilities and potential of people are enhanced through increasing their knowledge base in the form of providing training, scholarships, etc. These programs include:

- Training in India
- Training programme in the host country
- Scholarship and Fellowship
- Deputation of specialists
- Exposure visits

Figure 3 shows that the total slots in capacity building so far are 343,315. More than half of these slots are contributed by training programs in India, including the ITEC programs. Various other scholarships contribute to 26% of the total slots. Out of India's capacity-building slots, 12.8% contributed to training programs in partner countries and 4.2% to the deputation of experts for implementing various development projects and programs, as shown in Figure 4.

Figure 3 Total Number of Persons Trained. Figure 4: Distribution of Persons Trained (source: DevCoopIndia, 2022).

Unlike the OECD countries, which focus on basic safety and security, peace and development assistance largely focuses on conflict prevention and governing gaps. However, it fails to focus on the larger capacity and issues regarding political instability, which is also a factor in conflict and insecurity.

Areas	Sub areas	Focus	Forms	Concrete initiatives
Economic cooperation	Agriculture, trade, industry and FDI, SMEs, finance, regional integration	Food security, market access, exports to world markets and joint ventures	Cooperation, capacity-building, experience-sharing and TA	Financial support to African Union over mutually agreed programmes of continental importance Joint Platform for Discussion of Global Issues (South-South basis)
Political cooperation	Peace and security, civil society and governance	Governance structures, civil society, peacekeeping operations	TA, capacity building and cross fertilization of ideas	Roll out the Pan-African E-Network project
Science technology and research	Science and technology, ICT	Technology transfer, quality standards and ICT regulation	Experience sharing, cooperation	Increase ITEC scholarships
Social development	Education, health, water and sanitation, culture and sports, poverty eradication	MDGs, HRD, access to health care	Experience sharing, cooperation	
Terrorism		Regulation and governance	Partnerships	-
Infrastructure, energy and environment	-	PPP and creation of enabling environment	Cooperation	-
Media and communications	-	South-South communication	Cooperation	-

DAC code	CRS code	Category description
Core peacebuilding		
152		Basic safety and security / prevention
	15210	Security system management and reform
	15220	Civilian peacebuilding, conflict prevention and resolution
	15230	Participation in international peacekeeping operations
	15240	Reintegration and SALW control
	15250	Removal of land mines and explosive remnants of war
	15261	Child soldiers (prevention and demobilization)
Secondary peacebuilding		
151		Core government functions
	15110	Public sector policy and administrative management
	15111	Public financial management
	15112	Decentralisation and support to subnational government
		Inclusive political processes
	15113	Anti-corruption organisations and institutions
	15130	Legal and judicial development
	15150	Democratic participation and civil society
	15152	Legislatures and political parties
	15153	Media and free flow of information
	15160	Human rights
	15170	Women's rights organisations and movements, and government institutions
	15180	Ending violence against women and girls
	15190	Facilitation of orderly, safe, regular and responsible migration and mobility

Source: ODA is based on (OECD, 2022[a]), OECD Creditor Reporting System. <https://stats.oecd.org/index.aspx?DataSetCode=crsl>

Figure 5 Source: OECD's Official Peace and Development Assistance and India's approach to peace-building as developmental. Source: 1. OECD Creditor Reporting System 2022 and 2. Singh (2017) Africa-India Cooperation, Peace-building Through Development Partnership: An Indian Perspective

The OECD countries mainly focus on the governing gaps and basic security prevention. However, the mere absence of war is not peace. Focusing on issues such as food security, social development, ICT, and political and economic cooperation, India, as a major contributor, has reshaped the idea of peace-building into developmental assistance. Its lived experiences as a developing country influence the guiding principles and modalities for its development assistance (Choedon, 2021).

Figure 6 Source: <https://www.ciiximafriacaconclave.com/ProjectSummaryDetail.aspx>, updated as of August 14, 2020

Instead of a top-down, a demand-driven decentralised approach based on equity carrying similar historical experiences has led the case of India as a norm builder in reshaping the idea of peace. However, such an approach is not free from challenges, especially for the peacekeepers who are the early peacebuilders (Choedon, 2021). These peacekeepers, while being deployed during the conflict periods, lay the foundation to build and sustain peace by working on the capacity gaps that directly impact the civilians in such conflict areas. India has worked extensively in African countries such as Congo, Nigeria, Sudan, etc., although these assistances are not free from limitations that need to be addressed.

Peacekeeping and Peace-building: Challenges and Future Ahead

India has been actively contributing to peacekeeping operations since its independence, as Singh noted in 2017. The early peacekeepers played a vital role in the formation of peace-building. India has a proud legacy of contributing to UN Peacekeeping operations and is one of the largest troop contributors. It has provided approximately 275,000 troops to peacekeeping missions, with around 5,900 troops currently deployed in 12 UN Missions. Up until May 2023, 159 Indian Army soldiers have been martyred while serving in these missions. In addition to the current deployment, India has pledged to provide one Infantry Battalion Group and Corvette with a Helicopter as hard power and an Engineer Company and signal Company as Force enablers, to be deployed at the request of

the UN. It also recognises the need for women peacekeepers in conflict areas under UN mandate.

UN Mandate and Women, Peace and Security

A gender-oriented perspective was traditionally excluded from conflict analysis (Jansson & Eduards, 2012). Until the late 1980s, it was perceived as unrelated to international politics. The experiences and contributions of women to war or peace-making were rarely considered in the processes of policymaking (Gierycz, 2001). However, in the past two decades, there have been major developments in understanding gender equality and a gender perspective as imperative variables for international security.

The horrific stories of sexual violence during the armed conflict in the mid-1990s led to deeper concerns and interests in gender-related issues within the international community. The 1994 Rwandan Genocide and the 1992-1995 Bosnian Genocide brought the issues of conflict-related sexual violence to the attention of international actors (Engle, 2005). The first breakthrough in addressing conflict-related sexual violence was the 1998 Rome Statute of the International Criminal Court (Sivakumaran, 2007). It provided that rape and other sexual violence be considered a crime against humanity and war (A/CONF.183/9). This growing attention to the circumstances of women and young girls affected by armed conflict created momentum in the international policymaking arena (Tryggestad, 2009). International organisations such as the Women's International League for Peace and Freedom (WILPF International) established a group of global civil society organisations known as the Women and Armed Conflict Caucus played a vital role in drafting the aforementioned Agreed Conclusions of the CSW. The Women and Armed Conflict Caucus consisted of WILPF International, Amnesty International, International Alert, the Women's Commission for Refugee Women and Children, and the Hague Appeal for Peace, which was later transformed into the NGO Working Group on Women, Peace and Security (NGOWG) (Shepherd, 2008). The NGOWG lobbied the UN Security Council for the adoption of UNSCR 1325.

The lobbying also came from 'inside' the UN Security Council, mainly from three elected members: Bangladesh, Namibia and Jamaica (Basu, 2016). In March 2000, the president of the Security Council, Bangladeshi Ambassador Anwarul Chowdhury, released a press

statement on Women's Rights and International Peace (SC/6816), which highlighted the importance of women's participation in peace processes to the maintenance of international peace and security. In the same year, Namibia, in cooperation with the UN Department of Peacekeeping Operations (UNDPKO), hosted a workshop that resulted in the adoption of the Windhoek Declaration and the Namibia Plan of Action on Mainstreaming a Gender Perspective in Multidimensional Peace Support Operations (S/2000/693). Both these documents laid the conceptual foundations for UNSCR 1325, which was adopted in October 2000 under the presidency of Namibia.

The United Nations Security Council Resolution (UNSCR) 1325 is the first resolution of the Security Council that explicitly addresses the principle of gender equality. Hence, the resolution has been considered a major milestone in the struggle for gender equality in all aspects of peacemaking, peacekeeping and post-conflict recovery' (Willett, 2010). Even though it is not formally binding, UNSCR 1325 inaugurated a normative framework to advance gender equality in peace and security governance and policymaking – and through these processes, it aimed at improving gender equality outcomes for women in conflict zones. UNSCR 1325 was the first acknowledgement from the Security Council of the importance of women's participation in conflict prevention, conflict resolution and post-conflict peace-building and recovery. However, UNSCR 1325 placed protection from sexual violence under the Security Council's mandate, demonstrating its tangible impact on global peace and security (Jansson & Eduards, 2012).

By showing the gender-specific impact of conflict and post-conflict experiences on women, UNSCR 1325 called for the inclusion of a gender perspective in all peace and security programs and planning (Jansson & Eduards, 2012). India has also deployed Female Engagement Teams (FETs) in MONUSCO and UNISFA (the second largest women contingent after Liberia). India has deployed the Women Military Police in the United Nations Disengagement Observer Force (UNDOF) and women staff officers/military observers in various missions. To provide specialised training in peacekeeping operations, the Indian Army has also set up a Centre for UN Peacekeeping (CUNPK) in New Delhi (PIB, 2023). However, various challenges need to be addressed in terms of ground realities.

As per Lt. General JS Lidder, former force Commander, UNMIS and Deputy SRSG, Sudan, one of the major challenges to peacekeeping and building is to revise and recalibrate the existing standard and technical training to peacekeepers by bringing a context-specific revision. Since peacekeepers need to work in hostile situations. Therefore, cultural knowledge becomes imperative to understand conflict in any state. Another major challenge is the lack of representation of women in peacekeeping missions.

Women as Peacekeepers and Builders

Despite the UN Resolution on WPS, there have been obstacles to including women as peacebuilders. Many of these challenges are sustained due to the preexisting structural inequalities, which reinforces gender biases. Since negotiations and delegation on peace and security are largely dominated by men, they barely represent gender issues as a focal point (Goetz & Jenkiz, 2021). Since major challenges also stem from domestic actors bringing institutional or legal changes, hence external actors and bilateral donors such as the United Nations become imperative mediums for women peace activists to target the issue. However, many of these interventions by the multilateral or bilateral interventions have not met the adequate financial assistance for gender-responsive peace-building.

The United Nations, in 2010, declared gender-based spending to be at least fifteen per cent in post-conflict financing. However, as per the 2019 annual report of the Secretary-General to the Security Council on WPS, only seven per cent of UNDP's peace-building expenditure had the objective of gender equality. One significant factor of this neglect is the lack of leadership opportunities for women in peacemaking efforts. Such challenges and deadlocks within the United Nations provided middle powers such as India with a strategic and significant position in conflict management (Choedon, 2017). In terms of gender mainstreaming, not only the Indian female police unit handled the issues affecting Liberian women but also encouraged Liberian women to join the police force (Beri, 2008). However, such measures often reflect the existing challenges and barriers on the field. As per Major Rujula Shende, former Military Staff Officer, MONUSCO, the existence of gender bias, harassment and stereotypical assignment of tasks, and fewer women in leadership affects the participation of women in peacekeeping missions.

Country	Male	Female	Total
1. Ethiopia	7,750	588	8,338
2. Bangladesh	6,869	154	7,023
3. Rwanda	6,506	309	6,815
4. India	6,657	55	6712
5. Pakistan	6,192	26	6,218
6. Nepal	5,293	197	5,490
7. Egypt	3,186	1	3187
8. Indonesia	2,616	83	2,699
9. United Republic of Tanzania	2,468	178	2,646
10. Ghana	2,323	322	2,645
11. China	2,462	56	2,518

Figure 7 Source: UN Peacekeeping Troop Contributing countries by ranking as of 28/02/2018.

Although India is one of the top troop-contributing countries, as of December 2021, only 7.8% of the overall uniformed military, police, justice and correction personnel in field missions are women (UN et al., 2021). These gender barriers get further intertwined due to a lack of logistics and linguistic barriers. Many times, the good intent gets lost in translation. What is therefore required is a full, equal and meaningful participation of women in peace processes to advance the WPS Agenda (UN Resolution 1325) and advance gender parity in UN Police with recruitment, leadership, training and outreach. In Jan 2023, India deployed a women-only platoon of peacekeepers consisting of 25 soldiers of various ranks- as part of a battalion assigned to the United Nations Interim Security Force stationed in the hostile Abyei area that lies on the Sudan-South Sudan border. These challenges can be addressed if member states develop strategies and measures, such as active recruitment and provisions of adequate context-specific training and skill development.

Conclusion

Though the idea of peacekeeping and peace-building was institutionalised by the great powers (Bellamy & Williams, 2011) in the nineteenth and twentieth centuries, its constant limitations and failures in

negotiated settlements by applying similar liberal states frameworks and practices of democratic politics and free market policies (Conning & Call, 2017), led to the rise of countries like India to form its theory of peace-building. Its historical and lived experiences and socio-economic condition as a developing state provided India with a prime location, driving its motive through the emotional and ideational consideration to express solidarity with other developing states and paved the way as norm entrepreneurs in reshaping the idea of peace-building as developmental assistance through various methods such as Lines of Credits, Capacity-building programs. However, as the challenges persist in the field, what is indeed required is a context-specific revision and training within the UN WPS mandate in order to build peace effectively. Although the need for meaningful participation of women in peace-building processes has now been acknowledged, equal representation and engagement in the security agenda are imperative in order to establish peace within post-conflict states.

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